

FAIR Ecosystem Components

This iterative working paper presents a set of high-level interactive components necessary for a functioning FAIR¹ ecosystem. Operational repositories, and other (meta)data² related services are supported by common reference information managed in registries, and by evaluation processes consisting of standards and assessment methods.

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable digital objects (data and metadata³) are a necessary input to, and output from, ecosystems that integrate (one provider serves many) or federate (many providers interoperate) services.

Users of all kinds must be empowered to find and access (meta)data that supports interoperability and reuse. All ecosystem actors depend on machine⁴ and human⁵-mediated evaluation of digital objects' FAIRness.

These digital objects are not limited to datasets and their associated metadata as collected and created during research. A digital object could be any meaningful informational entity that is ultimately persisted as a set of bits on a digital medium. Such informational entities encompass policies, format standards, vocabularies/ontologies etc. These are often represented through file formats, or metadata schema, but are increasingly represented as RDF⁶ 'linked open data'.

The FAIRness of objects depends on their curation context, often provided by repositories. Repositories can be defined, in the broadest sense, as any service that accepts, stores and provides access to (meta)data. Repositories take varying levels of responsibility for curation including measures that maintain the (meta)data environment and those that take direct action on the digital objects themselves. Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR) are a specific type of standards-compliant and sustainable repository that is designed to monitor the need for, and to take responsibility for preservation actions on (meta)data. This 'active preservation' is undertaken in response to changes in infrastructure (people, processes and technologies) and to the composition, needs, and knowledge base of user communities.

Curation actions can ensure that (meta)data become FAIR digital objects. Ongoing curation in an active preservation context can ensure that those digital objects remain FAIR. A FAIR-enabling TDR has the long-term perspective to maintain the value of digital assets. FAIR + time requires active preservation.

In addition to repositories (ideally TDRs), other components are required to deliver an operational FAIR ecosystem across the research lifecycle. These include managed links to other

¹Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

²"(meta)data". This follows the approach used in the FAIR Principles to indicate data and/or metadata'.

³ The authors acknowledge that assumptions about data and metadata vary greatly across research and other 'data management' domains and that it is not always possible to clearly differentiate and separate them.

⁴ E.g. <https://www.f-ujj.net/>

⁵ E.g. <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/RDF>

digital objects, including software, and a range of (meta)data-related services, including registries.

The *Turning FAIR into Reality*⁷ report envisioned the FAIR ecosystem components presented in the diagram below. This paper assumes identifiers as critical to digital object management, and implies policies and data management plans (DMPs) as subsets of overall standards development, implementation and evaluation. Policies provide top down guidance across the ecosystem, while DMPs provide a consistent point of reference throughout the digital object lifecycle.

Figure 6. The components of a FAIR ecosystem

Diagram 1: **Components of a FAIR Ecosystem. Figure from *Turning FAIR into Reality***

To define, achieve and maintain FAIR digital objects and trustworthy services we require standard criteria and evaluation methods. The components presented in this paper present *registries* and *evaluation* as dependencies for *operational* (meta)data creation, curation, preservation and (re)use.

The need for infrastructure research and development (R&D) as a precursor to sustainable operations, and the dependency on clearer distinction of services (including repositories and registries) are discussed in the concluding remarks.

Diagram 2: **Repository Curators and (meta) data users: FAIR Object evaluation.**

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Turning FAIR into reality: final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data*, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

A mature FAIR ecosystem depends on a wider range of interdependent and coordinated components including actors with appropriate knowledge and skills. To achieve and maintain FAIR digital objects we require FAIR-enabling, trustworthy (meta)data services. Some aspects of the FAIR principles (E.g. richness, accuracy and relevance) can only be clarified and then evaluated based on the local context of the (meta)data, including domain and disciplinary expectations. Research repository evaluation focuses on the curation of research data objects: data and associated metadata and documentation created by, collected by, or of interest to researchers. A functioning ecosystem depends on a wider range of other objects including publications, standards, policies, procedures and data management plans (DMP¹³); these may be curated and preserved by the repository being evaluated, or by some other (meta)data service. In addition to providing the foundation of sustainable operations, these services and objects provide the evidence needed to undertake evaluations. These standards, and the processes that evaluate compliance, including self-assessments, peer reviews and formal audit and certification, must also be FAIR and trustworthy.

The full version of the diagram below (with a larger version in an Appendix) adds actors for Service and Software providers. It also adds criteria/evaluation components for software and services, and adds the vital components for content, training and assessment of skills. Together these present a high-level overview of these FAIR ecosystem components and their interactions and connections. Dotted lines with double-headed arrows represent some of the wide range of possible operational interactions.

Diagram 4: FAIR Vision: Ecosystem components (larger version as an appendix).

¹³ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/dmponline>

These interactive objects, repositories, software and services are on a journey towards trustworthy and FAIR operations. The operational components are not yet fully supported by evaluation and registry components.

Registries provide common-reference points for metadata about persistently identified objects and entities (people, organisations, grants, instruments etc) including:

- Repository registries with repository types and certification status
- (Meta)data standards registries and terminology registries that support FAIR (meta)data
- People Registries for unique identification of actors
- Registries of FAIR training and qualifications support skills development
- Registries of FAIR services¹⁴ that provide insight into FAIR across federations of partners and throughout the data lifecycle
- Research data object registries
- Registries of policies, including metadata about their machine-actionability

The alternative to these registry components is resource-intensive duplication of this information storage and curation, with an associated risk to consistency and accuracy.

Registries can support standards-compliant records linkage. Object registries (e.g. DataCite) can link to person registries (e.g. ORCID) to define actors and roles, and associate the objects with their curators through repository registries (e.g. Re3data or FAIRsharing). The interlinking of repositories to their community standards and policies (e.g. through FAIRsharing) including metadata about their machine-actionability supports the governance of a FAIR ecosystem by funders, service/software providers, research performing organisations and repositories.

Standards-compliant operations depend on clear criteria and assessment processes. The alternative to the evaluation components is underspecified or misaligned criteria, and a lack of assessment information.

The evaluation and registry components must also be based on defined criteria and be subject to evaluation.

Concluding Thoughts and Next Steps

A FAIR operational lifecycle, supported by FAIR registries, with FAIR-trained actors using FAIR-services and software would streamline the certification of FAIR-enabling Trustworthy Digital Repositories and their FAIR-data collections.

This FAIR (meta)data ecosystem model presents an idealised set of components and interactions. Not all of these exist, and those that do may need investment and improvement. With the exception of Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR), the other (meta)data services, including registries, are not yet sufficiently defined to allow their effective assessment.

This vision of a FAIR ecosystem would also benefit from a more in depth functional, process and lifecycle perspective. This would permit the more explicit inclusion of policies and DMPs, and the integration of a 'research and development' (R&D) component as a precursor to releasing products into the operational system. This R&D is broader than traditional software products and includes the design of services and the development of standard criteria and assessment processes. Newly developed components must then be transitioned from the R&D *project phase* to the sustainable operational *product/service phase* of their lifecycles.

¹⁴ The scope of, and approach to, FAIR services have not yet been fully defined.

Acknowledgements and Version History

Version 3.0

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This version has been revised after completion of the FAIRsFAIR project to act as an updated reference point for other strands of work on research infrastructure in general and FAIR in particular. The ecosystem components which support findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable metadata and data have direct relevance to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), but specific EOSC references have been removed as these components are not limited to a European context. They are broadly applicable to the global trend toward defragmentation and integration of data infrastructure into more efficient, interoperable infrastructure for data collection, creation, analysis, use and long-term preservation. The title and content of this version have removed the word 'vision' as all of the functions covered by the model already exist at some level. The question is how much investment we are prepared to make into moving from fragmented and duplicative approaches based on local practice towards common, sustainable solutions.

This version of the text covers the need for targeted research and development (R&D) as a precursor to deploying new functions into the operational, registry and evaluation components,

Version 2.0

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Version 2.0 of this paper has benefitted from a period of public comment during the FAIRsFAIR project. The authors would like to thank Susanna-Assunta Sansone (Oxford e-Research Centre) for valuable comments on version 1.0. The addition of object standards-bodies and assessment providers and the clarification that the concept of 'objects' applies beyond research data has broadened the scope of the model.

Version 1.0

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Initial release.

Appendix: Component Diagram (large)

